

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF STABILITY-INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF RELUGOLIX, ESTRADIOL HEMIHYDRATE AND NORETHINDRONE ACETATE IN ITS SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

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ABSTRACT

A simple, precise, accurate, and stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was successfully developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate in a synthetic mixture. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a YMC Trait C18 column with a gradient mobile phase of buffer and acetonitrile, at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and detection at 238 nm. The developed RP-HPLC method showed excellent performance with good chromatographic separation of Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate. Forced degradation studies were performed under various stress conditions such as acidic, alkaline, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic environments to indicated the stability-indicating capability of the method. The developed method effectively separated the drugs from their degradation products, confirming its suitable for stability studies. The method exhibited strong

linearity in the ranges of 200–600 µg/mL for Relugolix, 5–15 µg/mL for estradiol hemihydrate, and 2.5–7.5 µg/mL for Norethindrone acetate, with correlation coefficients exceeding 0.999, respectively. The method demonstrated excellent precision with %RSD values below 2%. The LOD values were 22.6 µg/mL, 0.74 µg/mL, and 0.46 µg/mL, while LOQ values were 68.6 µg/mL, 2.26 µg/mL, and 1.40 µg/mL. and good accuracy (98–102%

recovery) and the assay results were found to be within acceptable limits, respectively, indicating high reliability of the method. Overall, the method proved to be reliable and robust, making it suitable for routine quality control and analytical applications in pharmaceutical formulations.

KEYWORDS: Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, Norethindrone Acetate, RP-HPLC, Synthetic Mixture, Method Development, Method Validation, Stability-Indicating Method, Forced Degradation Studies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Uterine fibroids are common estrogen-dependent gynecological disorders characterized by chronic pelvic pain, abnormal uterine bleeding, and severe vasomotor symptoms that affect the quality of life in women of reproductive age.^[1] Relugolix, a GnRH receptor antagonist, which suppresses ovarian hormone production to manage symptoms associated with uterine fibroids and endometriosis.^[2] Estradiol Hemihydrate is incorporated as estrogen add-back therapy to alleviate hypoestrogenic side effects, while Norethindrone Acetate, a synthetic progestogen, provides endometrial protection against estrogen-induced hyperplasia.^[2,3] The combination of in a mixture is essential to ensure quality and effectiveness.

A stability-indicating RP-HPLC method helps in detecting the drugs even in the presence of degradation products. Therefore, this study focuses on developing and validating a simple, precise, and reliable method according to ICH guidelines.^[4] Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) is a widely used analytical technique for the simultaneous estimation of multiple drugs due to its accuracy and reliability.^[5]

Fig. 1. Structure of Relugolix.

Fig 2 Structure of Estradiol hemihydrate.

Fig 3 Structure of Norethindrone Acetate.

The literature review reveals that a few analytical methods have been reported, including RP-HPLC methods^[7,8], spectrophotometric methods^[9], LC/MS^[10], and stability studies^[11,12], either individually or in combination with other drugs in pharmaceutical dosage forms. However, a stability-indicating method has not been reported. Hence, the present study aims to develop and validate a new stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Relugolix, Estradiol hemihydrate & Norethindrone acetate in Synthetic Mixture suitable for routine quality control analysis.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Chemical and Reagents

Methanol, acetonitrile, orthophosphoric acid, potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer, and HPLC grade water were used for the RP-HPLC method development.

2.1.1. Analytical grade reagents Buffer Preparation: A 0.02 M Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate buffer was prepared by dissolving 2.72 g of potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate in 1 L of Milli-Q water using sonication. The pH was adjusted to 3 with diluted orthophosphoric acid.

2.2 Instrumentation

The analysis was carried out using a UV–Visible double-beam spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800, UV Probe software), HPLC system (Shimadzu LC-2010 CHT with UV detector, 100 μ L fixed loop injector, LC Solution software), analytical balance (Sartorius), USP Type II dissolution apparatus (Lab India DS 8000), digital pH meter (Lab India), ultrasonic bath (Athena Technology), hot air oven (Patel Scientific), and calibrated micropipettes (Eppendorf).

2.3 Standard Solution Preparation

Relugolix stock solution (4000 µg/ml): About 80 mg of Relugolix working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into 20 ml volumetric flask. To this, 10 mL methanol was added and dissolved by sonication. The solution was then diluted up to the mark with methanol and used as a stock solution.

Estradiol stock solution (100 µg/ml): About 10 mg of estradiol working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask. To this, 50 ml of methanol was added and dissolved by sonication. The solution was diluted up to the mark with methanol and used as a stock solution.

Norethindrone stock solution (50 µg/ml): About 10 mg of norethindrone acetate working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into 200 ml volumetric flask. To this, 100 ml of methanol was added and dissolved by sonication. The solution was diluted up to the mark with methanol and used as a stock solution.

Mix standard solution (400 µg/ml relugolix + 10 µg/ml Estradiol + 5 µg/ml Norethindrone): Pipetted out 1 ml of relugolix, 1 ml of estradiol and 1 ml of norethindrone stock solution in 10 ml volumetric flask. Volume was made upto the mark with diluent and used as a standard solution.

2.4.1 Sample Preparation

2.4.1.1. Sample Stock: Synthetic mixture 100 mg (equivalent 40 mg Relugolix, 1 mg Estradiol, and 0.5 mg Norethindrone Acetate) was weighed on butter paper. Powder was then transferred to 10 mL volumetric flask. To this 8 mL methanol was added and active contents were extracted in sonication for 15 minutes. The flask was allowed to cool down on room temperature and then the volume was made with methanol. The solution was then filtered through 0.45 µm Whatman PVDF syringe filter.

2.4.1.2. Sample (400 µg/ml Relugolix + 10 µg/ml Estradiol + 5 µg/ml Norethindrone Acetate): 1 mL of clear filtrate was then further diluted to 10 ml with diluent and used as a sample solution.

2.5. Chromatographic Condition

Separation was achieved on a YMC Trait C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm). The mobile phase consisted of Buffer and Acetonitrile (ACN) delivered in a gradient mode. the

gradient program was set as follows: 60:40 (Buffer: ACN) at 0.01 min, changed to 25:75 at 5.0 min, maintained up to 15.0 min, returned to 60:40 at 15.1 min, and maintained up to 20 min) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Detection was performed at 238 nm, the injection volume was 10 μ L, and the column temperature was maintained at 25 °C.

2.6. Force Degradation Studies

2.6.1. Acid Degradation

An aliquot (1 mL) of standard/sample solution was treated with 1 mL of 1 N hydrochloric acid in a 10 mL volumetric flask and kept at room temperature for 4 hours to induce acid degradation.

After the specified time, the solution was neutralized with 1 N sodium hydroxide, diluted to volume with diluent, mixed thoroughly, and analyzed by HPLC.

2.6.2. Base Degradation

An aliquot (1 mL) of the standard/sample solution was transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask and treated with 1 mL of 1 N sodium hydroxide for base degradation, followed by standing at room temperature for 4 hours. After the degradation period, the solution was neutralized with 1 N hydrochloric acid, diluted to volume with diluent, mixed well, and subjected to HPLC analysis.

2.6.3. Oxidative Degradation

An aliquot (1 mL) of the standard/sample solution was treated with 1 mL of 3% hydrogen peroxide and kept at room temperature for 4 hours to induce oxidative degradation. The solution was then diluted to volume with diluent, mixed well, and analyzed by HPLC.

2.6.4. Photolytic Degradation

Standard/Sample solution was placed in a clear container. The solution was exposed to direct sunlight for 24 hours. After exposure, the solution was suitably diluted with diluent. The prepared solution was analyzed by HPLC.

2.6.5. Thermal degradation

Standard/Sample solution was transferred into a tightly closed container. The solution was placed in a hot water bath maintained at 80 °C for 12 hours. After thermal treatment, the solution was cooled to room temperature. appropriate dilution was carried out with diluent and injected into the HPLC system.

2.7 Method Validation

The developed RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Relugolix, Estradiol hemihydrate, and Norethindrone acetate was validated as per ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines. The method was evaluated for system suitability, specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, LOD, LOQ, robustness, and assay, confirming its reliability for routine quality control analysis.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 FT-IR Spectroscopic Analysis

A small quantity of the API was analyzed using ATR-FTIR over the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} . The obtained spectrum was evaluated for characteristic functional group peaks and compared with reference spectra to confirm the identity of the API.

Table 1: FTIR Interpretation Relugolix.

Functional Group	Observed Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Reference Range (cm^{-1}) ^[13]
N–H Stretch	3258.91	3300–3200
C–H Stretch Aliphatic	2965.03, 2930.74, 2874.09	2970–2850
C=O Stretch	1670.82	1720–1640
C–N Stretch	1378.96	1380–1250
C–O Stretch (ether)	1303.39	1320–1210
C–F Stretch (aryl fluoride)	1151.97	1200–1000

Fig 4: IR spectrum of Relugolix.

Table 2: FTIR Interpretation Estradiol Hemihydrate.

Functional Group	Observed (cm^{-1})	Reference Range (cm^{-1})
O-H stretch	3606.6, 3502.5, 3292.3	3600–3200
C-H stretch	2856.4	2900–2700
C-H bending 1,2,4-trisubstituted	879.5	880 \pm 20

Fig 5: IR spectrum of Estradiol Hemihydrate.

Table 3: FTIR Interpretation Norethindrone acetate.

Functional Group	Observed (cm^{-1})	Reference Range (cm^{-1})
O-H stretch	3344.57	3500-3200
C-H stretching (aliphatic)	2899.01	2700-2950
C=O stretch	1654.92	1750-1650
C-H bending (aromatic)	1419.61, 1348.42	1450-1350

Fig 6: IR spectrum of Norethindrone acetate.

3.1.1. RP-HPLC method optimization condition

Fig 7: Determination of wavelength maximum (238nm).

3.2 Method development

Fig 8. Final HPLC Chromatogram of (400 µg/mL Relugolix + 10 µg/mL Estradiol + 5 µg/mL Norethindrone Acetate).

3.3 Force degradation studies

3.3.1 Acid Degradation

Fig 9-A: API Acid Degradation (Relugolix).

Fig 9-B: API Acid Degradation (Estradiol)

Fig 9-C: API Acid Degradation (Norethindrone Acetate).

Fig 9-D: Sample Acid Degradation.

3.3.2 Base Degradation

Fig 10-A: API Base Degradation (Relugolix).

Fig 10-B: API Base Degradation (Estradiol).

Fig 10-C: API Base Degradation (Norethindrone Acetate).

Fig 10-D: Sample Base Degradation.

3.3.3 Oxidative Degradation

Fig 11-A: API Oxidation Degradation (Relugolix).

Fig 11-B: API Oxidation Degradation (Estradiol)

Fig 11-C: API Oxidation Degradation (Norethindrone Acetate).

Fig 11-D: Sample Oxidation Degradation.

3.3.5 Photolytic Degradation

Fig 12-A: API Photolytic Degradation (Relugolix).

Fig 12-B: API Photolytic Degradation (Estradiol)

Fig 12-C: API Photolytic Degradation (Norethindrone Acetate).

Fig 12-D: Sample Photolytic Degradation.

3.3.6 Thermal Degradation

Fig 13-A: API Thermal Degradation (Relugolix).

Fig 13-B: API Thermal Degradation (Estradiol)

Fig 13-C: API Thermal Degradation (Norethindrone Acetate).

Fig 13-D: Sample Thermal Degradation.

Table 4: Forced Degradation result for Relugolix.

Condition	Sample Area	% Degradation (Sample)	API Area	% Degradation (API)
Acid	4910281	14.8	4931045	16.7
Base	5015322	12.9	5126652	13.4
Peroxide	5641490	2.1	5473689	7.6
Photolytic	5756500	0.1	5585219	5.7
Thermal	5679327	1.4	5703957	3.7

Table 5: Forced Degradation result for Estradiol.

Condition	Sample Area	% Degradation (Sample)	API Area	% Degradation (API)
Acid	388163	7.9	388499	5.1
Base	395169	6.3	388852	5.0
Peroxide	387199	8.2	383749	6.3
Photolytic	335199	20.5	320600	21.7
Thermal	398801	5.4	390833	4.6

Table 6: Forced Degradation result for Norethindrone Acetate.

Condition	Sample Area	% Degradation (Sample)	API Area	% Degradation (API)
Acid	371678	6.8	374804	5.3
Base	332531	16.6	333349	15.7
Peroxide	388578	2.6	389136	1.6
Photolytic	381555	4.4	388678	1.7
Thermal	370281	7.2	372375	5.9

3.4. Validation parameter

3.4.1. System suitability study

A mixed standard solution containing Relugolix (400 µg/mL), Estradiol Hemihydrate (10 µg/mL), and Norethindrone Acetate (5 µg/mL) was injected six times (n = 6) into the HPLC system.

Table 7: System Suitability Study.

Sr. No.	System Suitability Parameter	Relugolix Mean ± SD	%RSD	Estradiol Mean ± SD	%RSD	Norethindrone Acetate Mean ± SD	%RSD
1.	Retention Time (min)	3.988 ± 0.0022	0.06	6.532 ± 0.0031	0.05	9.910 ± 0.0033	0.03
2.	Tailing Factor	1.50 ± 0.0075	0.50	1.34 ± 0.0075	0.56	1.22 ± 0.0075	0.61
3.	Theoretical Plates (N)	8543 ± 14.4	0.17	24349 ± 27.3	0.11	28028 ± 27.3	0.10
4.	Resolution	—	—	15.0 ± 0.07	0.47	16.7 ± 0.07	0.42

3.4.2. SPECIFICITY

Specificity of the developed method for Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate was evaluated by: Injecting a blank solution to confirm absence of interference. Injecting a standard and Sample solutions.

No interfering peaks were observed at the respective retention times of Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate, confirming the specificity of the method.

Fig. 14. Diluent Chromatogram.

Fig 15: Standard Chromatogram.

Fig 16: Sample Chromatogram.

3.4.3. Linearity

Linearity was evaluated by preparing calibration curves at five concentration levels using least squares regression analysis.

Linearity Ranges: Relugolix: 200 – 600 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, Estradiol Hemihydrate: 5 – 15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, Norethindrone Acetate: 2.5 – 7.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

Appropriate aliquots from stock solutions were transferred into 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted to volume with mobile phase. Calibration curves were constructed by plotting.

Peak Area vs. Concentration

The following parameters were calculated: Slope, Y-intercept, Correlation coefficient (R^2)

The method demonstrated good linearity with R^2 values ≥ 0.999 for Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate

Table 17: Calibration Curve of Relugolix.

Sr. No.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Mean Area	SD	% RSD
1	200.00	3067797	5856	0.19
2	300.00	4480543	9938	0.22
3	400.00	6017193	12746	0.21
4	500.00	7460741	18424	0.24
5	600.00	8981514	16954	0.18

Fig 8: Linearity Data for Relugolix.

Table 9: Linearity Data for Estradiol Hemihydrate.

Sr. No.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Mean Area	SD	% RSD
1.	5.00	202237	518	0.25
2.	7.50	299807	220	0.07
3.	10.00	407879	103	0.02
4.	12.50	508515	654	0.12
5.	15.00	606373	76	0.01

Fig. 18: Calibration Curve of Estradiol Hemihydrate.

Table 10: Calibration Curve of Norethindrone Acetate.

Sr. No.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Mean Area	SD	% RSD
1	2.50	196040	172	0.08
2	3.75	289512	412	0.14
3	5.00	396017	615	0.15
4	6.25	488591	465	0.09
5	7.50	585633	74	0.01

Fig 19: Linearity Data for Norethindrone Acetate.

Fig. 20: Linearity Overlay.

3.4.4. Precision

Results were expressed as %RSD.

3.4.4.1. Repeatability

A standard solution containing Relugolix (400 µg/mL), Estradiol Hemihydrate (10 µg/mL), and Norethindrone Acetate (5 µg/mL) was injected six times (n = 6).

%RSD of peak areas was calculated.

Acceptance Criteria: %RSD ≤ 2.0%

Table 11: Repeatability Data of Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate.

Conc. of Relugolix	Peak area	Conc. of Estradiol Hemihydrate	Peak area	Conc. of Norethindrone Acetate	Peak area
400 µg/ml	5921212	10 µg/ml	409486	5 µg/ml	395598
	5925531		410290		395695
	5930306		409946		395634
	5935343		409738		395932
	5937540		409976		395585
	5942335		409735		396021
Mean	5932045	Mean	409862	Mean	395744
SD	7871.037206	SD	274.2687854	SD	186.1025703
%RSD	0.13	%RSD	0.06	%RSD	0.04

3.4.4.2. Intraday and Interday Precision

For intraday precision, standard solutions containing Relugolix (200, 400, 600 µg/mL), Estradiol Hemihydrate (5, 10, 15 µg/mL), and Norethindrone Acetate (2.5, 5, 7.5 µg/mL) were analyzed on the same day, while for interday precision the same three concentration levels were analyzed on three successive days, and %RSD was calculated for each level.

Table 12: Inter day and Intraday Precision.

Intraday Precision			Inter day Precision		
Relugolix					
Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Peak Area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD	Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Peak Area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
200	3069544 ± 10830.66	0.35	200	3223436 ± 54034.60	1.68
400	5970522 ± 16716.39	0.28	400	6196038 ± 14956.09	0.24
600	8910925 ± 26211.06	0.29	600	9078422 ± 145453.32	1.60
Estradiol Hemihydrate					
5	201440 ± 1589.30	0.79	5	202367 ± 1987.50	0.98
10	406838 ± 391.94	0.10	10	418540 ± 1423.81	0.34
15	588270 ± 1567.54	0.27	15	610382 ± 10066.70	1.65

Norethindrone Acetate					
2.5	199445 ± 474.22	0.24	2.5	202102 ± 2518.69	1.25
5	395129 ± 808.77	0.20	5	403960 ± 1162.00	0.29
7.5	589841 ± 1334.63	0.23	7.5	586052 ± 4156.43	0.71

3.4.5. Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantitation (LOQ)

LOD and LOQ for Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate were determined from calibration curve data. Calibration curves were prepared in triplicate, and the standard deviation (σ) of the Y-intercepts and mean slope (S) were calculated.

The following equations were used.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times (\sigma / S)$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times (\sigma / S)$$

Where:

σ = Standard deviation of intercept

S = Mean slope of calibration curve

Table 13: Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation data.

Sr. No.	Drug	LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
1	Relugolix	22.6	68.6
2	Estradiol Hemihydrate	0.74	2.26
3	Norethindrone Acetate	0.46	1.40

3.4.6. Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was determined by the placebo recovery (standard addition) method at three levels (50%, 100%, and 150%) with three replicates ($n = 3$).

A quantity of placebo equivalent (58.5 mg) to the formulation excipients was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask. About 8 mL of methanol was added, and the mixture was sonicated for 30 minutes. Finally, the solution was filtered through a 0.45 μm PVDF membrane filter.

% Recovery was calculated for each level.

Acceptance Criteria.

% Recovery should be between 98–102% and %RSD should be $\leq 2.0\%$.

Table 14: Accuracy Data for Relugolix.

Levels	Sets	mcg added	Mcg Found	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery	% RSD
50%	1	200.000	201.870	100.90	100.5	0.4
50%	2	200.000	200.850	100.40		
50%	3	200.000	200.170	100.10		
100%	1	400.000	405.880	101.50	101.1	0.5

100%	2	400.000	404.640	101.20	101.3	0.7
100%	3	400.000	402.000	100.50		
150%	1	600.000	603.280	100.50		
150%	2	600.000	609.630	101.60		
150%	3	600.000	610.470	101.70		

Table 15: Accuracy Data for Estradiol Hemihydrate.

Levels	Sets	mcg added	mcg Found	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery	% RSD
50%	1	5.000	4.910	98.20	99.6	1.3
50%	2	5.000	5.040	100.80		
50%	3	5.000	4.990	99.80		
100%	1	10.000	10.120	101.20	101.6	0.3
100%	2	10.000	10.170	101.70		
100%	3	10.000	10.180	101.80		
150%	1	15.000	14.840	98.90	99.4	0.4
150%	2	15.000	14.920	99.50		
150%	3	15.000	14.960	99.70		

Table 16: Accuracy Data for Norethindrone Acetate

Levels	Sets	mcg added	mcg Found	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery	% RSD
50%	1	2.500	2.540	101.60	100.9	0.6
50%	2	2.500	2.520	100.80		
50%	3	2.500	2.510	100.40		
100%	1	5.000	5.090	101.80	101.7	0.1
100%	2	5.000	5.090	101.80		
100%	3	5.000	5.080	101.60		
150%	1	7.500	7.470	99.60	100.0	0.4
150%	2	7.500	7.510	100.10		
150%	3	7.500	7.530	100.40		

3.4.7. Robustness

Robustness of the RP-HPLC method for Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate was evaluated (n = 3) by introducing small deliberate variations in chromatographic conditions.

Flow rate: ± 0.2 mL/min, Column temperature: $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$, Mobile phase composition: $\pm 2\%$ organic phase.

The effect of these changes on peak area, retention time, and resolution was studied

Acceptance Criteria: $\%RSD \leq 2.0\%$

The results demonstrated that the developed RP-HPLC method is robust and reliable under small variations in analytical conditions.

Table 17: Robustness Data of Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate.

	Drug	Area at Tem. (-5°C)	Area at Tem. (+5°C)	Area at Flow (-1%)	Area at Flow (+1%ml/min)	Area at Organic Phase-2%	Area at Organic Phase+2%
Mean Peak Area	Relugolix	5935794	5965565	6858978	5383639	6024360	6155138
	Estradiol Hemihydrate	404388	411368	467521	377598	406596	394971
	Norethindrone Acetate	387380	389018	447866	365128	387610	385372
% RSD	Relugolix	1.30	0.63	0.26	0.51	1.74	0.53
	Estradiol Hemihydrate	1.26	0.60	0.21	1.68	1.64	0.47
	Norethindrone Acetate	0.61	0.67	0.23	0.92	0.38	0.94
Theoretical Plates	Relugolix	8423	8030	6180	6456	7153	5895
	Estradiol Hemihydrate	25071	23840	26085	23077	26395	22569
	Norethindrone Acetate	27034	28691	27738	28426	28549	27390
Tailing Factor	Relugolix	1.47	1.53	1.54	1.50	1.56	1.53
	Estradiol Hemihydrate	1.36	1.32	1.37	1.34	1.36	1.35
	Norethindrone Acetate	1.22	1.24	1.23	1.22	1.22	1.22

3.4.8. Assay of Synthetic mixture

Table 18: Assay of Synthetic Mixture.

Drug	Label Claim (mg)	Mean Amount Found (mg)	Assay (% Mean \pm SD)	% RSD
Relugolix	40.0	39.3	98.2 \pm 0.148	0.15
Estradiol Hemihydrate	1.0	1.02	102 \pm 0.282	0.27
Norethindrone Acetate	0.50	0.49	98 \pm 0.327	0.33

4. CONCLUSION

A simple, precise, accurate, and stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was successfully developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate in a synthetic mixture. The developed method showed good chromatographic separation with acceptable system suitability parameters and low %RSD values. Validation results confirmed that the method is linear, precise, accurate, and sensitive within the studied concentration ranges.

Therefore, the proposed RP-HPLC method can be effectively applied for the routine quality control analysis and simultaneous estimation of Relugolix, Estradiol Hemihydrate, and Norethindrone Acetate in pharmaceutical formulations or synthetic mixtures.

REFERENCE

1. Stewart EA, Laughlin-Tommaso SK, Catherino WH, Lalitkumar S, Gupta D, Vollenhoven B. Uterine fibroids. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*, **2016**; 2: 16043.
2. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Myfembree (relugolix, estradiol, norethindrone acetate) tablets: Prescribing information. Silver Spring (MD): FDA, 2021.
3. International Council for Harmonisation (ICH). Q8(R2): Pharmaceutical Development. Geneva: ICH, **2009**.
4. International Council for Harmonisation (ICH). Q2(R1): Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology. Geneva: ICH, **2005**.
5. Snyder LR, Kirkland JJ, Glajch JL. *Practical HPLC Method Development*. 2nd ed. New York: Wiley, **1997**.
6. ICH. Stability testing of new drug substances and products. Q1A (R2), current step, **2003**, 4: 1-24.
7. Kumar MS, et al. "RP-HPLC method development and validation of Relugolix". *Int J Chem Biochem Sci*, **2023**; 24(6): 850–5.
8. Al-Nimry SS, Altanni BM, Haddad RH. "RP-HPLC method for estimating norethindrone in plasma and tissues following administration of a controlled release nanoparticulate liquid formulation". *Indian J Pharm Sci*, **2020**; 82(4): 593-600.
9. Ajitha K, Kimbahune R, Mubeen G, Pai Y. "Simultaneous spectrophotometric estimation of norethindrone acetate and ethinyl estradiol in formulation". *Asian Chem Sci J.*, **2016**; 16(4).
10. Lolla S, Gubbiyapp KS. "Bio-analytical method development and validation for the quantitation of Relugolix in plasma samples by LC-MS/MS: application to bioavailability study in rabbits". *Rasayan J Chem*, **2023**; 16(1): 494–501.
11. Gautam P. "Method development and validation of stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the determination of female hormones in hormone concentrates creams", **2017**; 3(1).
12. Azeez R, Bairagi VA, Azeez Z. "A novel validated stability indicating QbD based RS method by HPLC for the estimation of impurities of norethindrone in norethindrone acetate and their degradation as per ICH Q2 guideline". *Int J Pharm Sci*, **2024**; 2(2): 297-315.

13. P.S Kalsi spectroscopy of organic compounds, 2010; 2.55.